

Key to world genera of Rhinophorinae (Calliphoridae)

[v2 - updated March 2026]

Original version: 10.3897/zookeys.903.37775

by Pierfilippo Cerretti¹ and Thomas Pape²

¹*Department of Biology and Biotechnologies “Charles Darwin”, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy orcid.org/0000-0002-9204-3352*

²*Natural History Museum Denmark, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. orcid.org/0000-0001-6609-0609*

The following dichotomous key to the world genera of Rhinophorinae is a revised and corrected version of that presented by Cerretti et al. (2020). Following the identification of several inaccuracies in the original key (Ziegler & Špalek Tóthová 2025; in red), the placement of *Nesodexia* within the Rhinophorinae (Cerretti et al. 2024; in blue), and the description of new species of *Acompomintho* that necessitated a redefinition of the genus boundaries (Ziegler & Špalek Tóthová 2025; Liu et al. in preparation; in red), the present version provides a more complete and reliable tool for assigning specimens to genus.

Caveats: Unless explicitly stated otherwise, references in the text to figures refer to those in the original version of the key (Cerretti et al. 2020).

1. Body ground colour metallic green or blue-violet. Postalar wall with a tuft of fine setulae..... [*Alvamaja* Rognes; Polleniidae]
- Body ground colour not metallic green or blue-violet, at most shiny black. Postalar wall bare or with setulae, as in *Nesodexia corsicana* and in Afrotropical rhinophorine-like Polleniidae, see couplets 8, 13, 17, 22]..... 2

2. Brachypterous, micropterous or apterous specimen (Fig. 4H), female only 3
- Wing fully developed, male or female..... 4

3. Tergite 7 and sternite 7 forming a sclerotised, dorsoventrally flattened oviscapt (Fig. 13K–N)..... ***Axinia*** Colless (in part)

- Segment 7 normally developed, i.e., not modified into a dorsoventrally flattened oviscapt **Bezzimyia** Townsend (in part)

- 4. Vein M₁ running nearly straight or evenly curved forward to wing margin (Figs 9B, C; 10D, M, N; 16I; 17J; 18F), i.e., without a distinct bend 5
- Vein M₁ with a distinct, sometimes shallow bend that can be well removed from wing margin (e.g., Figs 9A, D–F, K, L; 10B, C, E–L) or very close to it (Fig. 9G), or M₁ not reaching wing margin (i.e., ending freely in the wing membrane) (Fig. 9H–J).. 11

- 5. Shiny black or brown flies, usually with bright yellow antenna or, more rarely, with variously patterned legs; with very short setae on head, scutum and abdomen, of approx. the same size as the smallest clothing setae (Fig. 4C–E). Vein CuA+CuP not reaching wing margin (i.e., ending freely in the wing membrane). Male: postpedicel characteristically rounded-subtriangular (axe-head-like and shorter than maximum distal width) (Fig. 6C–F), the thickened posterior margin abutting the enlarged, sunken face or anterior margin forming two or more lobes; arista absent or very short (i.e., distinctly shorter than length of postpedicel) and arising apically or sub-apically on postpedicel (Fig. 6C–F). Female: tergite 7 and sternite 7 forming a strongly sclerotised, dorsoventrally flattened and evenly curved, usually long oviscapt (Fig. 13K–N) **Axinia** Colless
- Body colour varies from black to yellow, microtomentum present or absent; setae of head and thorax usually normally developed. Male: postpedicel usually not triangular in lateral view (if so, then postpedicel much longer than its maximum distal width and vein CuA+CuP reaching wing margin), arista arising in proximal half (Fig. 18C, E). Female: terminalia not modified 6

- 6. Antenna short, at most as long as minimum height of gena (usually much shorter) (Figs 16D, F; 17F, H). Antenna arising distinctly below middle of compound eye. Tarsus of fore leg strongly laterally compressed (Figs 16A, H; 17B, E). Palpus strongly reduced, approx. 1–2 times as long as wide
..... **Neotarsina** Cerretti and Pape
- Antenna much longer than minimum height of gena, arising at or above middle of compound eye. Tarsus of fore leg not laterally compressed. Palpus usually well developed, if reduced then mouthparts vestigial 7

7. First postsutural supra-alar seta well developed, at least as long and robust as posterior notopleural seta (Fig. 13B, F)..... 8
- First postsutural supra-alar seta absent or minute (Fig. 13E)..... 9
8. Head longer than high and facial profile not receding. Prementum at least as long as head height and labella narrow. Antenna brown to black. Upper half of facial plate carinate (Fig. 13A). Postalar wall usually with at least 1 small setula. Male: cerci normally developed and medially not fused into a syncercus; surstylus articulated (i.e., not fused) to epandrium; extension of dorsal sclerite of distiphallus divided medially into two sclerites; median process of ventral sclerotisation of distiphallus not fused to base of ventral sclerotisation
[*Morinia* “*carinata* species group” (in part); Polleniidae]
- Head higher than long (even if slightly so) and facial profile receding (Figs 5E; 7H). Prementum usually shorter than height of head, if approx. as long as head height and labella narrow, then antenna pale yellow. Face not carinate. Postalar wall bare. Male: cerci very short and medially fused into a syncercus; surstylus fused to epandrium; extension of dorsal sclerite of distiphallus not divided medially; median process of ventral sclerotisation of distiphallus very long, narrow and fused to base of ventral sclerotisation***Rhinodonia*** Cerretti, Lo Giudice and Pape
9. Vein CuA+CuP not reaching wing margin (i.e., ending freely in the wing membrane, Fig. 10M). First aristomere at most as long as wide, second aristomere approx. 4 times as long as wide. Mouthparts strongly reduced (vestigial). Male: proclinate orbital setae absent; postpedicel normal, i.e., not divided longitudinally into lobes; cerci not fused medially, distally well separated as two pointed processes; surstylus fused to epandrium..... ***Rhinopeza*** Cerretti, Lo Giudice and Pape
- Vein CuA+CuP reaching wing margin (Fig. 9B). First aristomere at least 4 times as long as wide, second aristomere at least 8 times as long as wide (at least half as long as third aristomere). Mouthparts normally developed or strongly reduced. Male: 0–1 proclinate orbital setae; postpedicel varying from normal to branching into three lobes; cerci medially fused into a syncercus or distally well-divided into two pointed processes; surstylus not fused to epandrium 10

10. Mouthparts normally developed (Fig. 18A, C, E). Male: 1 proclinate orbital seta; postpedicel entire, i.e., not divided longitudinally into lobes (Figs 18A, C, E); anterodistal margin of first and second tarsomeres of hind leg without modified setae; cerci medially fused into a syncercus (Fig. 18G).....
..... ***Kinabalumyia*** Cerretti and Pape
- Mouthparts strongly reduced (proboscis very short, though palpus well developed). Male: proclinate orbital setae absent; postpedicel divided longitudinally into three lobes (Figs 4B; 6B); anterodistal margin of first and second tarsomeres of hind leg provided with a comb of flattened setae, which are distally jagged; cerci proximally fused, distally divided into two pointed processes (similar to the condition shown in Fig. 15F)..... ***Aporeomyia*** Pape and Shima
11. Vein M₁ not reaching wing margin (i.e., ending freely in the wing membrane) (Fig. 9H–J)..... 12
- Vein M₁ reaching wing margin (Figs 9A, D, K, L; 10B, E, H–K) or fused to vein R₄₊₅, so that cell r₄₊₅ is petiolate (Figs 9E, F; 10C, F, G, L)..... 15
12. Male and female without proclinate orbital setae. Male: surstylus fused to epandrium
..... ***Bezzimyia*** Townsend (in part)
- Male and female with at least 1 proclinate orbital seta. Male: surstylus either freely articulating with or fused to epandrium..... 13
13. Prementum long and slender, at least as long as head height, and labella narrow. Postalar wall usually with at least 1 small setula. Postpronotum with 2 setae and facial profile not receding.....
[*Morinia lactineala* (Pape), *Morinia* “*carinata* species group” (in part): Polleniidae]
- Prementum shorter than head height, and labella fleshy and normally developed. Postalar wall bare. Facial profile receding or not; if not receding then postpronotum with 3 setae arranged in a right-angled triangle..... 14
14. Facial profile not receding, i.e., vibrissal angle distinctly in front of anterior margin of eye (Fig. 7E). Postpronotum with 3 setae arranged in a right-angled triangle (or nearly so) (as in Fig. 2C). Male: 1 proclinate orbital seta. Female: 2–3 proclinate orbital setae..... ***Oplisa*** Rondani (in part)

- Facial profile receding, i.e., vibrissal angle approx. in line with or behind anterior margin of eye (head with postcranial surface oriented vertically) (Figs 7B; 8B–E). Postpronotum with 1–3 setae, if 3 then arranged in a line or an obtuse triangle (as in Fig. 2B). Male: at least 2 proclinate orbital setae. Female: 3–5 proclinate orbital setae 24

- 15. Posterior lappet of metathoracic spiracle distinctly larger than anterior lappet (Fig. 13H). Female: thorax yellow, brown or black..... **16A**
- Anterior and posterior lappets of metathoracic spiracle approx. of equal size and standing out from spiracular rim (i.e., almost perpendicular to pleural surface) (Fig. 13I), sometimes lappets not differentiated at all (Fig. 13J). Female: thorax usually black or brown, rarely yellow 18

- 16A. Lower calypter broad as usual in calyptrate flies, i.e., not tongue-shaped. Postalar wall with setulae. In combination: parafacial bare; facial ridge with a few decumbent setae on lower third; palpus well developed; wing cell r_{4+5} open; vein R_1 bare; vein $CuA+CuP$ reaching wing margin. Large forms (body length: 7.5–11.0 mm) endemic to Corsica ***Nesodexia*** Villeneuve
- Lower calypter narrowly tongue-shaped as in usual rhinophorines. Postalar wall bare. Other combination of characters 16B

- 16B. Vein R_1 setose dorsally along full length. Vein R_{4+5} with setulae dorsally extending from base to approx. level of bend of vein M_1 . Cell r_{4+5} open (Fig. 14A, C). Parafacial bare. Facial ridge with a row of setae on lower 2/3 (Fig. 14A, D). Vibrissa well developed. Palpus absent. Female: head, thorax, legs and abdomen mostly pale yellow (Fig. 14). Male unknown
..... ***Maurhinophora*** Cerretti and Pape
- Vein R_1 bare. Vein R_{4+5} with a few short setulae confined at base or bare. Cell r_{4+5} open or petiolate. Parafacial setulose at least on upper half (Figs 6J; 13C, D). Facial ridge bare or with a few decumbent setae on lower third. Palpus well developed17

- 17. Vein R_{4+5} with a few short setulae confined to base. Cell r_{4+5} petiolate (Fig. 9E, F). Anterior lappet of metathoracic spiracle without setae. Female: thorax yellow (Fig. 4G). Male: at least tip of wing membrane smoky (Fig. 9E); frons very narrow (i.e.,

- head almost holoptic), without proclinate or lateroclinare orbital setae.....
..... **Baniassa** Kugler
- Vein R₄₊₅ bare. Cell r₄₊₅ open. Anterior lappet of metathoracic spiracle with setae. Female: thorax black or brown. Male: wing membrane evenly yellowish; frons broad with at least 1 proclinate or lateroclinare orbital seta (i.e., head non-holoptic).....
.....[*Morinia* “*carinata* species group” (in part): Polleniidae]
18. First postsutural supra-alar seta present and well developed, as long as or longer than notopleural setae (Fig. 13B, F)..... 19
- First postsutural supra-alar seta absent or very short, distinctly shorter and weaker than notopleural setae (Fig. 13E, G) 24
19. Palpus absent. Facial ridge with a row of setae on lower 2/3 (Fig. 14D). Vein R₁ entirely setulose dorsally. Vein R₄₊₅ with setulae dorsally, extending from base to approx. level of bend of vein M₁. Head, thorax, legs and abdomen mainly yellow (Fig. 14)..... **Maurhinophora** Cerretti and Pape
- Palpus present and usually well developed. Facial ridge with at most a few setulae just above vibrissa. Vein R₁ bare. Vein R₄₊₅ dorsally with a few short setulae confined to base or with 1 strong setula. Body colour variable 20
20. Palpus, tibiae, femora, pleural sclerites of thorax and sides of abdomen yellow (Fig. 5D). Head distinctly higher than long in lateral view. Facial ridge nearly straight. Lunule bare. Abdominal tergites 3 and 4 with strong, erect median discal setae (Fig. 11G). Male tergite 6 not differentiated **Queximyia** Crosskey
- Palpus, tibiae, femora, pleural sclerites of thorax and sides of abdomen black or blackish-brown. Head varying from longer than high to higher than long. Facial ridge usually concave. Lunule bare or with setulae. Abdominal discal setae, if present, not as above. Male tergite 6 always present 21
[If both thorax and abdomen are black, and abdomen is without median discal setae, run also from couplet 41]
21. Lunule with setulae (Fig. 13C). Katepimeron with at least 1 seta anteriorly, often with several setae scattered on the entire surface. Male with or without orbital setae (lateroclinare and/or reclinate).....

-**Phyto** Robineau-Desvoidy (in part, except *P. pauciseta* species group)
- Lunule bare. Katepimeron bare. Male with orbital setae (laterocline and/or reclinate)..... 22
22. Upper half of facial plate carinate (Fig. 13A) (sometimes only slightly so). Base of vein R₄₊₅ dorsally bare. Postalar wall usually with a tuft of short setulae (rarely bare). Anterior lappet of metathoracic spiracle usually with 1–7 setae. Prementum varying from normally developed to long and slender with narrow labella
-[*Morinia* “*carinata* species group” (in part): Polleniidae]
- Facial plate not carinate. Base of vein R₄₊₅ dorsally with 1 long setula (Fig. 10B). Postalar wall bare. Anterior lappet of metathoracic spiracle without setae. Prementum distinctly shorter than head height and labella unmodified (i.e., broad)..... 23
23. Facial profile moderately receding, i.e., vibrissal angle in line with antennal insertion (postcranial surface oriented vertically) (as in Fig. 7D). Male with orbital setae (only 1, strong)
-**Comoromyia** Crosskey
- Facial profile not receding, i.e., vibrissal angle produced forwards and in front of antennal insertion (Fig. 7I). Male without procline orbital setae
-**Rhinomorinia** Brauer and Bergenstamm (*R. sarcophagina* (Schiner), in part)
24. Antenna distinctly shorter than height of gena (Figs 7B–D, F; 8A, B). Gena at least 0.5 times as high as compound eye; if less, then (i) mouthparts strongly reduced, vestigial and (ii) postangular section of vein M₁ absent (Figs 4K; 9H–J). Male with procline orbital setae
- 25
- Antenna at least as long as height of gena (usually distinctly longer), and gena at most 0.35 times as high as compound eye; if more, then mouthparts normally developed and vein M₁ complete
- 29
25. Cell r₄₊₅ open or vein M₁ ending freely in wing membrane (i.e., postangular section of vein M₁ absent)
- 26
- Cell r₄₊₅ long petiolate; petiole 0.8–2.5 times as long as postangular section of vein M₁ (Figs 4L; 10L)..... 32
26. Postangular section of vein M₁ absent and vein ending freely in wing membrane (Fig.

- 4K). Mouthparts strongly reduced, vestigial (Fig. 7B, C). Scutellum with only 1 pair of defined marginal setae (subapicals), diverging or subparallel. Thorax and abdomen characterised by a thick cover of silvery microtomentum, which is brilliant in anterodorsal view (Figs 4K; 11A) (*M. argyriiventris*, *M. basilewskyi*), or dull black (*M. asetosa*). Lunule bare. Male: trichia on arista bottlebrush-like.....
.....**Melanophora** Meigen (in part, *M. argyriiventris* species group)
- Vein M₁ complete, i.e., reaching wing margin (Figs 9L; 10J; 15E). Mouthparts small, but normally developed. Scutellum usually with 2 pairs of well-developed marginal setae (basals and converging or crossed apicals). Microtomentum of thorax and abdomen different. Lunule bare or with setulae. Male: trichia on arista usually not bottlebrush-like (except **Marshallicona** Cerretti and Pape) 27
27. Male and female without proclinate orbital setae (Fig. 8A). Wing membrane infuscate with 3 whitish, hyaline spots (Figs 5J; 10J)..... **Trypetidomima** Townsend
- Male and female with at least 1 proclinate (or lateroclinate) orbital seta (Figs 7F; 15C). Wing membrane different 28
28. Vein R₁ dorsally setose on distal 1/4. Vein CuA+CuP not reaching wing margin (i.e., ending freely in the wing membrane). Costal sector cs₅ longer than costal sector cs₂ (Fig. 15E). Thorax blackish brown (Fig. 15A). Katepimeron bare. Lunule bare. Male: arista bottlebrush-like; 4–5 proclinate orbital setae (Fig. 15C, D).....
.....**Marshallicona** Cerretti and Pape (live habitus Fig. 1C)
- Vein R₁ dorsally bare. Vein CuA+CuP reaching wing margin. Costal sector cs₅ shorter than costal sector cs₂ (Fig. 9L). Thorax mainly yellow (Fig. 5B). Katepimeron usually with a few setulae anteriorly. Lunule usually setulose. Male: arista bare; 1–2 proclinate orbital setae **Parazamimus** Verbeke
29. Vein R₁ entirely setulose dorsally. Scutellum with only 1 pair of defined marginal setae (subapicals), diverging or subparallel. Head shape strongly modified especially in male, with sunken face and vibrissal angle conspicuously projected forward and turned inwards apically (Fig. 7L). [Wing infuscate with 3 or 4 whitish spots (as in Fig. 10J). Male: proclinate orbital setae present; first aristomere elongated, more than twice as long as wide] **Shannoniella** Townsend
- Vein R₁ bare dorsally, if with 1–3 setulae distally, then scutellum with at least 3

- marginal setae. Head shape not as described above..... 30
30. Facial profile receding, i.e., vibrissal angle approx. in line with or behind anterior margin of eye (head with postcranial surface oriented vertically) (Figs 6A, K, L; 7B–D, F, G; 8A, C) 31
- Facial profile not receding, i.e., vibrissal angle distinctly in front of anterior margin of eye (Figs 6G; 7A, E, I, J, K) (Ziegler & Špalek Tóthová 2025, figs 1, 2, 11, 12; Liu et al. in prep.) 41
31. Cell r_{4+5} long petiolate (Figs 4L; 5C, G, L; 10C, F, G, L).....32
- Cell r_{4+5} open (Figs 9A, D, G, K, L; 10B, E, J, K), closed at wing margin (Fig. 10H, I) or vein M_1 ending freely in membrane (Fig. 9J)..... 34
32. Parafacial with a row of long robust setae (Fig. 8E). Male: arista not bottlebrush-like. Female: wing without whitish posterior subapical spot **32A**
- Parafacial with fine setulae at most on upper half (Fig. 13D). Male: arista bare, plumose or bottlebrush-like. Female: wing with or without whitish posterior subapical spot 33
- 32A.** Antenna distinctly shorter than eye height. Second aristomere not elongated
..... **Ventrops** Crosskey (in part) [*V. stuckenbergi*]
- Antenna at least as long as eye height Ziegler & Špalek Tóthová 2025, figs 20–23).
Second aristomere elongated, 2–3 times as long as wide
..... **Acompomintho** Villeneuve (in part) [*A. itoshimensis*, *A. lobata*]
33. Both sexes with 3–7 proclinate orbital setae. Male: trichia on arista bottlebrush-like (Figs 7B; 13D); posterior margin of sternite 5 with a deep median cleft. Female: wing mainly brownish with whitish posterior subapical spot.....
..... **Melanophora** (in part, *M. roralis* species group)
- Male with 0–2, female with 1–3 proclinate orbital setae. Male arista bare to short pubescent, not bottlebrush-like; sternite 5 with almost straight posterior margin. Female: wing varying from hyaline to variously patterned but without whitish posterior subapical spot **Paykullia** Robineau-Desvoidy

34. Facial ridge with robust setae on lower 1/2 or more. Vein CuA+CuP reaching wing margin. Female: postpedicel with a row of setae medially or dorsally (Fig. 6L)....
 **Malayia** Malloch
- Facial ridge with only a few decumbent setulae reaching at most the lower 1/3. Vein CuA+CuP usually not reaching wing margin (except in *Bixinia winkleri* from Australia). Female: postpedicel without setae 35
35. Parafacial bare. Lateral vertical seta not differentiated from postocular row (as in Fig. 8A)..... 36
- Parafacial setose at least on upper half (Figs 6A; 8E). Lateral vertical seta well differentiated from postocular row (Fig. 8D, E); if not differentiated, then lunule with setulae..... 38
36. Bend of vein M₁ distinctly rounded and very close to wing margin (Fig. 9G). Antenna distinctly longer than compound eye height, and facial ridge longer than frons (Fig. 6K).....**Bixinia** Cerretti, Lo Giudice and Pape
- Bend of vein M₁ well removed from wing margin (Fig. 9K, L). Antenna shorter than compound eye height and facial ridge shorter than frons (Fig. 8A, C)..... 37
37. Male and female with at least 2 proclinate orbital setae (Fig. 8C). Wing infusate mostly along veins, without whitish spots. Lower calypter without long, blackish setulae along margin. Posterior margin of eye indented in lateral view (Fig. 8C). Eye enormously developed so that gena and parafacial are practically obliterated. Male cerci very short
 **Ventrops** Crosskey (in part, *V. milichioides* species group)
- Male and female without proclinate orbital setae (Fig. 8A). Wing infusate with 3 whitish, hyaline spots (Figs 10J). Lower calypter with long, blackish setulae along margin. Posterior eye margin not indented (Fig. 8A). Eye large but not enormously developed so that both gena and parafacial are distinct. Male cerci well developed
 **Trypetidomima** Townsend
38. Antennal insertion distinctly above eye middle. Antenna long, at least as long as eye height. Second arismere elongated, 2–3 times as long as wide.....
 **Acompomintho** Villeneuve

- Antennal insertion at or below eye middle (Figs 6A; 8D, E). Antenna distinctly shorter than eye height. Second aristomere at most as long as wide..... 39

- 39. Male and female without proclinate (or lateroclinate) orbital setae (Fig. 6A). Lunule setose. Legs largely red (Fig. 4A). Male: surstylus fused to epandrium
..... **Apomorphyto** Cerretti, Lo Giudice and Pape
- Male and female with proclinate orbital setae (Fig. 8D, E). Lunule bare. Legs black or blackish-brown. Male: surstylus not fused to epandrium 40

- 40. Abdominal tergites extensively covered with whitish-grey reflecting microtomentum except along posterior margins of tergites 3–5 and along a narrow longitudinal median vitta. Head and thorax extensively covered with grey reflecting microtomentum. Basicosta yellow. Male: arista pubescent, longest trichia distinctly longer than maximum, basal diameter of arista. Body length: 6 mm
..... **Ventrops** Crosskey (undescribed species from South Africa)
- Head, thorax and abdomen shiny black or nearly so, i.e., with microtomentum sparse or almost absent. Basicosta black or yellow. Male: arista apparently bare, i.e., trichia clearly shorter than its maximum diameter. Body length less than 4 mm
Ventrops Crosskey (in part, *V. hannemariae* and *V. aethiopicus* species groups)

- 41. Distal section of CuA+CuP (i.e., distal to junction with CuA) approx. 1/2 of total length of CuA+CuP (Fig. 9C, D; 10A). Parafacial much narrower (approx. 1/4 or less) than width of postpedicel and bare in lower half. Anterior katepisternal seta weak and at most 2/3 as long as posterior one 42
- Distal section of CuA+CuP approx. 3/4 of total length of CuA+CuP (Figs 9A, E, G; 10E–G), but with approx. 1/2 of total length of CuA+CuP then parafacial wider (1.5 or more times as wide as width of postpedicel), with setae on lower half. Anterior katepisternal seta robust and more than 2/3 as long as posterodorsal katepisternal seta 43

- 42. Anterior katepisternal seta more than 1/2 as long as posterior seta. Second aristomere slightly elongated, approx. 1.5 times as long as wide (Fig. 6G, H). Male: fore tarsus not elongated or compressed (Fig. 4F); wing membrane hyaline or evenly smoked (Fig. 9D)..... **Azaisia** Villeneuve

- Anterior katepisternal seta distinctly less than 1/2 as long as posterior seta. Second aristomere at most as long as wide (Fig. 7A). Male: fore tarsus greatly elongated and laterally compressed (Fig. 4J); wing membrane darkened around distal third of vein R₂₊₃ (Fig. 4J)..... **Macrotarsina** Schiner

- 43. Lunule (Fig. 13C), notopleuron and katepimeron setose. Median process of ventral sclerotisation of distiphallus interrupted proximally and not connected to ventral plate (Fig. 12G) **Phyto** Robineau-Desvoidy (*P. paucisetata* Herting)
- Setae never present on lunule, notopleuron and katepimeron simultaneously. Median process of ventral sclerotisation of distiphallus not interrupted, running from ventral plate to tip of phallus 44A

- 44A. Postpedicel about 2.0–5.0 times as long as pedicel and 3.0–4.5 times as long as wide. Second aristomere elongated, 2–5 times as long as wide
..... **Acompomintho** Villeneuve (in part)
[*A. carmanica*, *A. gavryushini*, *A. sinensis*, *A. monticola*]
- Antenna short and stout, postpedicel about 1.0–2.5 times as long as pedicel and 1.2–2.7 times as long as wide. Second aristomere not elongated..... 44B

- 44B. Postpronotum with 3 setae arranged in right-angled triangle or nearly so; if only 2 setae (*Stevenia gilasiani*), then parafacial with strong setae in lower half.....
..... 45A
- Postpronotum with 3 setae arranged in a line or in an obtuse triangle; if only 2 setae, then parafacial bare..... 47

- 45A. Cell r4+5 usually long petiolate, the shortest petiole is as long as crossvein r-m [*Stevenia acutangula*]. Parafacial with strong, bristly setae in lower half. Mid tibia with at least 2 anterodorsal setae **Stevenia** Robineau-Desvoidy
- Cell r4+5 narrowly open, closed at wing margin or very short-petiolate (petiole, when present, shorter than crossvein r-m). Parafacial bare or with hair-like setulae or with strong setae [*Tricogena rubricosa*]. Mid tibia usually with 1, rarely with 2 anterodorsal setae 45B

- 45B. Parafacial bare or with hair-like setulae in upper half only, at its narrowest point 0.04–

- 0.10 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Fronto-orbital plate at level of middle of scape, when seen in profile, 0.13–0.20 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Claws of fore leg in both sexes shorter than fifth tarsomere. Lobes of male sternite 5 large, but extend distally not to the posterior edge of the 5th tergite **Oplisa** Rondani (in part)
 [*O. hertingi*, *O. japonica*, *O. nudiseta*, *O. oldenbergi*, *O. pollinosa*, *O. tergestina*]
- Parafacial with setulae or setae in full length, at its narrowest point 0.12–0.20 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Fronto-orbital plate at level of middle of scapus, viewed in profile, 0.28–0.33 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Claws of fore leg in males at least as long as fifth tarsomere. Lobes of male sternite 5 very large, extending posteriorly at least to the level of the posterior margin of the 5th tergite **Tricogena** Rondani [*T. caucasica*, *T. grandiloba*, *T. rubricosa*]
47. Arista plumose, i.e., longest trichia approx. 2.5 times as long as maximum diameter of arista (Fig. 8B)..... **Tromodesia** Rondani
- Arista bare or with trichia at most 1.5 times as long as maximum diameter of arista 48
48. Base of vein R₄₊₅ bare or with a few, short, fine setulae, distinctly shorter than crossvein r-m. Vibrissal angle more or less in line with antennal insertion (postcranial surface oriented vertically) (Figs 6G; 7E) 49
- Base of vein R₄₊₅ with at least 1 strong setula, longer than crossvein r-m, with or without additional shorter setulae. Vibrissal angle produced forwards and in front of antennal insertion (Figs 7I; 12C) 51
49. Cell r₄₊₅ open or closed at wing margin, very rarely petiolate but petiole at most approx. half as long as crossvein r-m 50
- Cell r₄₊₅ with a petiole 1.2–2.5 times as long as crossvein r-m 52
50. Frontal vitta, palpus (Figs 6G, H; 7A) and basicosta yellow 42
- Frontal vitta, palpus and basicosta black..... **Metoplisa** Kugler
51. Cell r₄₊₅ open or closed at wing margin, rarely petiolate with petiole approx. half as long as crossvein r-m. Scutum with 2 presutural microtomentose vittae. Palpus at

- least as long as postpedicel (Fig. 7I). Male: head not holoptic, with upper reclinate orbital setae usually differentiated (except *R. capensis*)]
- **Rhinomorinia** Brauer and Bergenstamm (in part)
- Cell r_{4+5} with a petiole 1.2–2.5 times as long as crossvein r-m. Scutum dark with no presutural microtomentose vittae differentiated. Palpus varying from shorter to longer than postpedicel. Male: head almost holoptic or dichoptic, with or without upper reclinate orbital setae 52
52. Parafacial entirely bare. Palpus shorter than postpedicel. Lunule bare. Male: head almost holoptic, upper reclinate orbital setae not differentiated (Fig. 12A, C). Male terminalia as in Fig. 12D, E **Melanomyoides** Crosskey
- Parafacial with a row or short setulae. Palpus longer than postpedicel. Lunule with setulae. Male: head dichoptic, with upper reclinate orbital setae usually differentiated **Rhinophora** Robineau-Desvoidy

References

- Cerretti, P., Badano, D., Gisondi, S., Lo Giudice, G., Pape, T. (2020) The world woodlouse flies (Diptera, Rhinophoridae). *ZooKeys* 903: 1–130. doi: 10.3897/zookeys.903.37775
- Cerretti, P., Yan, L., Narayanan Kutty, S., Szpila, K., Nania, D., Tintea, R., Mei, M., Pape, T. (2024) Phylogenomics resolves long-standing questions about the affinities of an endangered Corsican endemic fly. *Journal of Insect Science*, 24, 9. doi: 10.1093/jisesa/ieae073
- Liu, Z.j., Ascenzi, A., Cheng, X.-l., Li, H-q, Zhang, C-t, Pape, T., Zhang, D., Cerretti, P. (in preparation) Review of woodlouse flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae: Rhinophorinae) from China, with descriptions of four New Species.
- Ziegler, J., Špalek Tóthová, A. (2025) Species of the genera *Acompomintho* and *Tricogena* (Diptera: Calliphoridae: Rhinophorinae), and their phylogenetic position based on molecular and morphological data. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 65(2): 419-449. doi: 10.37520/aemnp.2025.031